

D1: Overview on reference ontologies and necessary application ontologies compiled.

<i>Reporting for Project:</i>	<i>MetaMap³</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>27.12.2021 (Version 1.0)</i>
<i>Work package:</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>Partner:</i>	<i>HMGU</i>
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Introduction

The MetaMap³ project deals with the compilation, generation, enrichment and mapping of machine-readable and interoperable metadata schemes for exemplary data of the three domains Health, Earth & Environment and Aeronautics, Space & Transport. The objective of deliverable D1 is to explore the availability of domain-specific semantic resources and to evaluate their potential for our intended metadata mapping. We therefore compiled an overview on reference ontologies and necessary application ontologies classified by domain that support the semantic annotation of epidemiological, environmental and spatial resources.

Overview on domain-specific ontologies

Table 1 lists the ontologies that were taken into account during the first 6 months of the project. The ontologies have been visually inspected using the software Protégé¹. Not all the ontologies we have considered are still in active development. For example, according to the OBO Foundry repository, the use of the Epidemiology Ontology EPO² is deprecated. At the time of writing, the Epidemic Marketplace³, a case study for storing and describing epidemiological resources based on the Semantic Web concepts, is no longer online. Due to the interdisciplinary setting of the MetaMap³ project, finding a set of suitable, comprehensive and actively maintained ontologies proved to be a challenge especially for the Health field.

We therefore shifted our focus towards standards and catalogs. Table 2 shows domain-specific standards and catalogs for metadata of the Health domain. While most of the available metadata standards were developed for clinical data or settings, we could identify three suitable platforms which fit to our epidemiological metadata and cohort setting. Based on our search, we decided to start with uploading our metadata to the NFDI4health StudyHub⁴, an inventory of German health studies on COVID-19 which was started only recently and is based on the Maelstrom catalog. An alternative platform is MOLGENIS, which will be employed by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 project EXPANSE (<https://expanseproject.eu/>) as part of their harmonization effort. Since our use case cohort GINI/LISA is part of the EXPANSE project, we will also upload our metadata into MOLGENIS.

We created RDA accounts and uploaded first metadata schemes into the HMC Metadata Standards Catalog⁵ which are summarized in Table 3. In addition, two compliance checkers for NetCDF files have been added. The NetCDF data type is relevant for our MetaMap³ project as the metadata of the drought monitor, our use case of the domain Earth and Environment, are stored as NetCDF files. The tools check whether a given NetCDF file complies with the community standard (e.g. Climate and Forecasts Metadata Convention). To map the NetCDF files to the XML files of the Domain Aeronautics, Space & Transport we tested the R package “geometa”⁶. The R package "geometa" provides tools to handle geographic metadata in the frame of the OGC/ISO 19115 and 19139 (XML) standards.

Table 1. Overview of the ontologies relevant for our domains Health, Earth and Environment, Space and Transport.

Health (HMGU)				
Acronym	Ontology	Repository	Url of the repository	Domains
EPO	Epidemiology Ontology	OBO	http://www.obofoundry.org/	epidemiology
EXO	Exposure Ontology	OBO / AberOWL / CTD	http://www.obofoundry.org/ http://aber-owl.net/#/ http://ctdbase.org	epidemiology, environment
CIDO	Coronavirus Infectious Disease Ontology	OBO / AberOWL	http://www.obofoundry.org/ http://aber-owl.net/#/	health, pandemic
IDO- COVID- 19	The COVID-19 Infectious Disease Ontology	AberOWL	http://aber-owl.net/#/	health, pandemic
ONE	Ontology for Nutritional Epidemiology	OBO / AberOWL	http://www.obofoundry.org/ http://aber-owl.net/#/	epidemiology
GENEPIO	Genomic Epidemiology Ontology	OBO / AberOWL	http://www.obofoundry.org/ http://aber-owl.net/#/	epidemiology
Earth and Environment (UFZ) / Space and Transport (DLR)				
Acronym	Ontology	URL of the ontology		Domains
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) Ontology	https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/sosa		sensor, observation
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network Ontology	https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/w3c-ssn		sensor
CF	Climate and Forecast (CF) standard names parameter vocabulary	http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/cf/cf-property		climate
CF- Feature	Climate and Forecast (CF) features	http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/cf/cf-feature		climate
AWS	Meteorological sensor ontology	https://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/meteo/aws		sensor, weather
OIL- E/ENVRI	Open Information Linking for Environmental science research infrastructures	http://oil-e.net/ontology/		infrastructure, environment
ODM2	Observations Data Model Version 2	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/		observation
GEMET	GEneral Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/themes/		environment
Further ontologies of interest		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NeoGeo Spatial Ontology (spatial) • OGC GeoSPARQL (gsp) 		

Table 2. Overview of metadata standards, catalogs and platforms for the domain “Health”.

Item	Type	Url
HL7 FHIR	Standard	https://hl7.de/ueber-hl7/
CDISC ODM	Standard	https://www.cdisc.org/standards/data-exchange/odm
Snomed CT	Standard	https://www.snomed.org/
Maelstrom	Catalog / Platform	https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/catalogue
NFDI4health Studienportal	Catalog / Platform	https://www.nfdi4health.de/task-force-covid-19/studienportal.html
MOLGENIS	Catalog / Platform	https://data-catalogue.molgenisccloud.org/apps/docs/#/catalogue/README

Table 3. Tools, schemes and organizations that have been uploaded into the HMC and RDA Metadata Standards Catalog.

Item	Type	Url	HMC	RDA
Cf-checker	Tool	https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/msc/t69	x	x
IOOS Compliance Checker	Tool	https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/msc/t70	x	x
Attribute Convention for Data Discovery	Scheme	https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/msc/m111	x	x
Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)	Scheme	https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/msc/m112	x	*
Operational Data Model (ODM)	Scheme	https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/msc/m113	x	x
Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)	Organization	-	x	x
Health Level Seven International (HL7)	Organization	-	x	*
Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC)	Organization	-	x	x
Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research	Organization	-	x	x
Helmholtz Zentrum München	Organization	-	x	x

x = resource has been added

* = resource already present

Conclusion and Outlook

After reviewing the reference ontologies for the different fields, we now consider ontology mapping as long-term goal. The trade-off between the standardization effort and the benefit of a stronger semantic needs to be considered, thus a stronger semantic is not always the optimal choice. In this first half year of the project, we decided on our metadata use cases (UFZ: drought monitor; DLR: land cover; HMGU: GINI/LISA cohort), metadata standards (ISO 19115 for UFZ/DLR) and metadata mapping (to be performed by location (spatial coverage) and date (time coverage)). Based on the scientific context of the project and specifically no default standard available for HMGU, we slightly shifted the focus. Our current priority is to standardize and enrich our metadata based on the standards of the respective domains and to upload the metadata to catalogs.

References

[1] <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

[2] Pesquita, C., Ferreira, J.D., Couto, F.M. *et al.* The epidemiology ontology: an ontology for the semantic annotation of epidemiological resources. *J Biomed Semant* **5**, 4 (2014).

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[3] Lopes, Luis F., et al. "Epidemic marketplace: an information management system for epidemiological data." *International Conference on Information Technology in Bio-and Medical Informatics*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2010.

[4] <https://covid19.studyhub.nfdi4health.de/>

[5] <https://msc.datamanager.kit.edu/>

[6] Emmanuel Blondel. "geometa: Tools for Reading and Writing ISO/OGC Geographic Metadata in R (0.6-4)." Zenodo, 2020 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5512147>